

DESCRIPTION OF "DIVANI FONIY" EXEMPLAR TEHRAN UNIVERSITY

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the description of the manuscript copy of Alisher Foni-Navoi's "Divani Foni" numbered 2866, which is kept in the Central Library of the University of Tehran in Iran. The article also clarifies the number of odes and ghazals contained in this copy.

There are several manuscript copies of Alisher Foni - Navoi's "Divani Foni" in the world's funds. Manuscript copies of this divan are currently stored in the manuscript collections of the libraries of France, Turkey and Iran. In particular, it is known that there are three copies in Tehran. One of them, inventor number is 15002, is the exemplar in the library of the Islamic Shoora Majlis, which was initially briefly described in the catalog of Ibn Yusuf Shirazi, in the introduction to the first edition of "Divani Foni" in Iran by Ruknuddin Humayunfarruh, and in the dissertation of Hamid Sulaiman, and the second is the copy, under the inventor number 4992, stored in the same library under the title "Khazoyinul Qasida". The third copy in Iran is stored in the Central Library of Tehran University under the number 2866 inv. In this article, we describe a manuscript copy of the Divan, inv. 2866, kept in the Central Library of Tehran University in the Islamic Republic of Iran.

The remarkable aspect of this copy is that, probably because it was discovered later, there is no information about this exemplar in the research documents on the "Divani Foni". Only a brief description of this copy is given in the second edition of the "Divani Foni" in Iran, published by Sayyid Abbas Rustokhiz Sonchorki in 1400 AH (2022 AD). It states the following information: - "This copy is Hiravi's Devani Foni, stored in the Central Library of Tehran University under the inv. number 2866. It contains the ode "Sittayi Zaruriya" and the ghazals with the letters /- "alif", ب- "be" and ت- "te". The source is lost. Several of its leaves are missing. On the second page there is a short preface in six lines. This preface does not belong to the devan. There is no preface for the devan. In our opinion, this preface was written later by another person to provide a brief introduction to the composition of the devan and to Alisher

Navoi. This is also confirmed by the fact that the preface and the handwriting of the qasids and ghazals in the devan are different. It states the following:

دیوان فانی هروی.

نسخه نفیس و بی نظیر دیوان فانی مشتمل بر منظومات زیر از قصاید و غزل.

1 - منظومه روح القدس

2 - منظومه و قصیده عین الحیات که عدد ابیاتش را مطابق آنست بقا 104 تعیین فرموده

3 - منظومه و قصیده منهاج النجاة

4 - منظومه و قصیده قوت القلوب

سپس غزلیات است تاریخ کتاب که بحروف نهجی مروف باشد تعداد کلی ابیات قریب یکهزار و صد هشت. تاریخ تحریر کتاب تصریح نشد ولی قریب خط کاغذ گواهی شد که در اوایل قرن نهم بوده است.

شرح حال فانی - فانی از شعرای معاصر سلطان حسین میرزا بابقرا است و نام و ترجمه حال و زندگانی اش در تذکره مجالس النفایس امیر علیشیر مذکور است. دیوان فانی دیده نشده و نسخه دگر آن در دست نیست. طبعش بسیار خوب و دارای قدرت کامل و در اصناف نظم با وقوف و خوش فرسجه باشد¹.

"Hirawi's "Divani Foni".

The unique and elegant copy of "Divani Foni" consists of the following qasidas and ghazals.

- 1) Ruhul Quds Manzuma;
- 2) Aynul Hayot Qasida and Manzuma, with 106 verses;
- 3) Minhajun Najat Qasida and Manzuma;
- 4) Qutul Qulub Qasida and Manzuma

After them are the ghazals. The history of the book is known from the letters in it, the number of verses in it is about one thousand eight hundred.

The date of compilation of the book is not written, but according to the appearance of the letter and the testimony of the paper, it may be the end of the 10th century.

Foni's biography - Foni is one of the contemporary poets of Sultan Husayn Mirzo Bayqara, and his name, biography and life are mentioned in the commentary of Amir Alisher "Majoliun Nafoyiz".

"Divani Foni" has not been seen and we do not have another copy of it. His potencial (talent) is very good and has perfect power and is aware of the nuances of poetry and is beautiful.

¹ دیوان فانی هروی. علی شیر فانی. کتابخانه مرکزی دانشگاه تهران. ش 2866. ص. 1.

The palaeographic and cadical characteristics of the source are as follows: the size of the source: 20x12. The cover is dark black, made of hard cardboard. The ink is black. The writing is in Nasta'lik. There is a table. There are no miniatures. There is a small title at the beginning of the odes. There is also a place for the title before the ghazals, but the title is not drawn, the place is empty. As a result of water damage, some words in the poems have faded, and some pages have been lost. This copy consists of 38 pages. Each page has 15 verses.

The first page contains poems in Turkish that are not related to Navoi's Persian divan, written horizontally.

From the next page, there is a small title, the text inside which is impossible to read. The odes begin below the title. Three odes are complete in this copy. They are the odes "Ruhul Quds", "Aynul Hayot" and "Qutul Qulub". Three odes are incomplete. These are "Tuhfatul Afkor", only the first 8 verses of this ode exist, and the remaining verses have not been preserved due to the loss of the pages. Also, the title of the ode at the beginning of this ode is incorrectly written, that is, the

title of the ode "Tuhfatul Afkor" is written in red ink as "Minhojun Najot":

The incomplete ode in the poem is the ode "Minhojun najot". The leaf containing its first 26 verses has been lost. The next ode is the ode "Nasimul khuld", which only has 33 verses. Below is a table of the odes, their size and leaf number:

The qasids are followed by ghazals. The ghazals in this copy begin with the following

Nº	Qasidas	Verses of Qasidas	Pages
1	"Ruhul quds"	Complete - 132 verses	1 - 10 - pages
2	"Aynul hayot"	Complete - 106 verses	10 - 17 - pages
3	"Tuhfatul afkor"	Incomplete - 8 verses	17 - page
4	"Minhojun najot"	Incomplete - 112 verses	18 - 25 - pages
5	"Qutul qulub"	Complete - 120 verses	25 - 33 - pages
6	"Nasimul xuld"	Incomplete - 33 verses	33 - 35 - pages

couplet:

ای خاک سر کوی تو گشتن هوس ما
بر پای سگت بوسه زدن ملتمس ما²

The next page, where the ghazal "Hamd" is located, has been repaired, resulting in some words from the ghazal being erased:

² دیوان فانی هروی. علی شیر فانی. کتابخانه مرکزی دانشگاه تهران. ش 2866. ص. 27.

The fifth ghazal in this copy is also damaged, namely the page containing the first 4 verses of the 7-verse ghazal. As a result, the first verse and some lines of the ghazal are unreadable:

The number of ghazals and pages in this copy are listed in the following table:

TABLE:

No	LETTERS	AMOUNT OF GHAZALS	PAGES
1	ا	25	36 - 52
2	ب	15	52 - 61
3	ا	9	62 - 65
4	ت	14	66 - 76

The table above shows that the pages were rearranged during the repair of this copy. The total number of ghazals in this copy is 63, some of which are incomplete due to missing pages. We have included only two ghazals whose praise has been preserved in this count. None of the ghazals in this copy have titles, but a space has been left for a title. The ghazal, which begins with the following matla, concludes this copy:

شام هجران مرا عکس رخ یار کجاست
بهر آن عکس می آینه کردار کجاست³

In conclusion, it can be said that among the few manuscript copies of Alisher Foni's "Divani Foni", it is the most damaged, does not cover many genres in its content, and also has a small number of ghazals, and although the copying was not completed, it is in ruins, but it is of particular importance. The fact that this copy has a paogir on each page to ensure the consistency of titles and pages, and its antiquity also increases its importance in literary source studies.

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6. کتابخانه مرکزی دانشگاه تهران. ش 2866. علی شیر فانی. دیوان فانی هروی.

³ دیوان فانی هروی. علی شیر فانی. کتابخانه مرکزی دانشگاه تهران. ش 2866. ص. 76.